

THE BEHAVIOR OF UNIAXIALLY LOADED

GRAPHITE/EPOXY PLATES WITH HOLES

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The objective of this investigation was to study the deformation and failure of uniaxially loaded graphite/epoxy plates with holes and to determine the influence of hole size on failure. The specimens were $[0/\underline{+45}/90]_S$ and $[0_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ laminates with holes of various diameters. They were instrumented with strain gages and photoelastic coatings. Strains on the hole boundary become nonlinear at strain levels between 0.006 and 0.0065 corresponding to applied stresses of 110 MPa (16 ksi) and 172 MPa (25 ksi) for the $[0/\underline{+45}/90]_S$ and $[0_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ laminates, respectively. In the former, the maximum strain on the hole boundary reaches values up to twice the ultimate strain of the unnotched laminate. In the $[0_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ specimens the compressive stress on the hole boundary around the loading axis produces local delamination causing stress and strain redistribution. In the quasi-isotropic laminates failure initiates at points 22.5-deg off the horizontal axis, where the interlaminar and membrane shear stresses reach maximum values with early nonlinear strain response. In the $[0_2/\underline{+45}]_S$ specimens, in the case of larger holes failure initiates at locations approximately 18-deg from the horizontal, in the case of smaller holes the outer 0-deg plies through the hole tend to delaminate. The effect of hole diameter on strength reduction was satisfactorily described by using the average stress criterion with characteristic lengths of 3.8 mm and 5 mm. There is a critical hole diameter below which the laminates become insensitive to it. In the case of the quasi-isotropic laminate, strength reduction was found to be independent of notch geometry, i.e., specimens with holes and cracks of the same size had nearly the same strength.

Introduction

Stress distributions around circular holes in composite plates have been treated analytically using linear anisotropic elasticity (1,2) and finite element methods (3-6). The latter can be used to account for material inhomogeneity, nonlinearity, and inelasticity. Related analytical failure studies have been limited and not entirely successful. Experimental methods, using strain gages, photoelastic coatings and moiré, have proven very useful in verifying theoretical solutions in the linear range and supplementing them in the nonlinear range (6-12). Experimental methods are especially useful in studying failure modes.

Most of the failure analyses of composites with stress concentrations, such as holes or cracks, are based on the assumption of linear material behavior and on failure criteria carried over from isotropic materials. Greszczuk (13), for example, used a form of the Hill criterion based on distortion energy to determine the ultimate load and location of failure on the hole boundary. Waddoups, Eisenmann and Kaminski (14) analyzed failures in composite plates with holes using linear elastic fracture mechanics and assuming the existence of two fictitious Griffith type cracks on the boundary of the hole. No physical interpretation was given to these fictitious cracks. Cruse (15) analyzed a similar problem by modeling the circular hole with a straight crack having an equivalent stress distribution near its tip. Recently, Whitney and Nuismer (16) proposed simplified stress fracture criteria which explain discontinuity size effects without applying linear elastic fracture mechanics. They are based on the actual stress distributions near the discontinuity and assume the existence of a characteristic dimension. According to one criterion proposed, failure occurs when the average stress over this characteristic dimension equals the unnotched tensile strength of the material. Comparison with results from uniaxial tensile tests showed satisfactory agreement between predicted and measured strengths for a narrow range of values of the characteristic dimension.

The objective of this investigation was to study experimentally the deformation and failure of uniaxially loaded graphite/epoxy plates with holes of various diameters and to determine the influence of hole size on failure. The study, limited to $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ and $[0_2/\pm 45]_S$ laminates, consisted of testing uniaxial unnotched and notched specimens. The approach used was to measure deformations by means of experimental strain analysis techniques, determine strain distributions, failure modes and strength reduction ratios. Results were compared with analytical predictions.

Experimental Procedure

The graphite/epoxy system used was the SP-286T300 (3M Company) obtained in the form of 30.5 cm (12 in.) wide and 0.127 cm (0.005 in.) thick prepreg tape. The unidirectional material was fully characterized with the determination of moduli, Poisson's ratios, strengths and ultimate strains. Uniaxial properties of the $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ and $[0_2/\pm 45]_S$ eight-ply laminates without stress concentrations were also determined. The notched specimens were 12.7 cm (5 in.) wide and 56 cm (22 in.) long eight-ply laminates with central circular holes of diameters 2.54 cm (1.00 in.), 1.91 cm (0.75 in.), 1.27 cm (0.50 in.) and 0.64 cm (0.25 in.). The area around the hole was instrumented with strain gages and photoelastic coatings. These included miniature strain gages of 0.38 mm (0.015 in.) gage length bonded on the curved edge of the hole. Two specimens of each hole diameter and each of the two layups mentioned before were tested under uniaxial tension to failure. The specimens were loaded through friction by bolting

gripper plates to the tabbed ends. They were loaded in increments in a 120,000 lb Riehle testing machine. At every load level strains and photoelastic fringe patterns were recorded.

Results for $[0/+45/90]_S$ Laminate

Strains on and near the hole boundary and in the far field were plotted as a function of applied stress as shown in Fig. 1 for the case of the 2.54 cm (1.00 in.) diameter hole. In general, strains on the hole boundary become nonlinear at a strain level of 0.006 corresponding to an applied stress of 110 MPa (16 ksi). This is attributed to first-ply failure of the 90-deg plies which have an ultimate strain of 0.0054. The measured strain concentration factor is very close to the theoretical value of 3 in the linear range. Maximum strains on the hole boundary vary with applied stress at an increasing rate reaching values up to twice the ultimate strain of the unnotched laminate.

Isochromatic fringe patterns in the photoelastic coating reveal points of high birefringence concentration on the hole boundary at points located between 67-deg and 71-deg from the loading axis (Fig. 2). The variation of fringe order and tangential strain at the 0-, 71- and 90-deg locations on the hole boundary is shown in Fig. 3. The fringe order at the 0-deg

Fig. 1 Vertical Strains Along Horizontal Axis of $[0/+45/90]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimen With a 2.54 cm (1 in.) Diameter Circular Hole Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading

Fig. 2 Isochromatic Fringe Patterns in Photoelastic Coating on $[0/+45/90]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimen With a 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) Diameter Circular Hole Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading at Three Levels of Applied Stress: (a) 142 MPa (20.5 ksi), (b) 182 MPa (26.4 ksi) and (c) 223 MPa (32.3 ksi)

Fig. 3 Fringe Order and Tangential Strain at Three Locations on the Hole Boundary for $[0/+45/90]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimen

location, corresponding to the compressive strain at that point, varies linearly to failure. The birefringence at the 90-deg location varies linearly up to an applied stress of approximately 110 MPa (16 ksi) corresponding to a tangential strain of approximately 0.006, equal roughly to the failure strain of the 90-deg plies. The fringe order, hence the tangential strain, at the 71-deg location becomes nonlinear at a lower stress, approximately 83 MPa (12 ksi). Thereafter, it increases at a faster rate overtaking and exceeding the fringe order (strain) at the 90-deg location. This is attributed to the fact that at the 67.5-deg location the interlaminar and membrane shear stresses reach maximum values and the circumferential normal and shear strains increase nonlinearly and more rapidly than at any other point. Failure, consisting of delamination and tensile cracking, initiates at these characteristic off-axis points. Typical failure patterns are shown in Fig. 4.

Results for all specimens with holes of various diameters are summarized in Table I. The last column in this table shows the strength reduction ratio, i.e., the ratio of the strength of the notched specimen to that of the unnotched. This ratio is plotted versus hole diameter in Fig. 5. The point stress and average stress criteria were used to describe the effect of hole size (16). According to the average stress criterion, failure occurs when the axial stress averaged over a characteristic distance a_0 from the hole boundary along the transverse axis equals the strength of the unnotched laminate (Fig. 6). The strength reduction ratio as predicted by this criterion is expressed as

Fig. 4 Failure Patterns in Uniaxially Loaded $[0/+45/90]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Plates With Holes of Various Diameters (Hole Diameters are: 0.64 cm (0.25 in.), 1.27 cm (0.50 in.), 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) and 2.54 cm (1.00 in.))

Fig. 5 Strength Reduction as a Function of Hole Radius for $[0/+45/90]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Plates With Circular Holes Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading

Table I. Uniaxially Loaded $[0/+45/90]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimens With Circular Holes

Hole Diameter $2a$ cm (in)		Modulus E_{xx} GPa (10^6 psi)		Poisson's Ratio ν_{xy}	Strain Conc. Factor k_ϵ	Strength S_{xx} MPa (ksi)	Maximum Strain at Failure ($10^{-3}\epsilon$)	Strength Reduction, S_{xx}/S_o
2.54	(1.00)	56	(8.1)	0.30	3.00	229 (33)	>22	0.455
2.54	(1.00)	54	(7.9)	0.30	3.00	209 (30)	11.5	0.416
1.91	(0.75)	56	(8.1)	0.28	2.85	243 (35)	18.5	0.482
1.91	(0.75)	53	(7.6)	0.29	2.90	219 (32)	-	0.436
1.27	(0.50)	54	(7.9)	0.31	2.96	247 (36)	18.6	0.493
1.27	(0.50)	56	(8.2)	0.30	2.64	263 (38)	-	0.521
0.64	(0.25)	54	(7.9)	0.30	-	271 (39)	> 9.4	0.534
0.64	(0.25)	56	(8.1)	0.25	2.96	282 (41)	19	0.562
0.48	(0.187)					309 (45)		0.658
0.48	(0.187)					286 (41)		0.608
0.16	(0.062)					381 (55)		0.811
0.16	(0.062)					388 (56)		0.825
0.04	(0.016)					463 (67)		1
0.04	(0.016)					434 (63)		1
0.02	(0.008)					505 (73)		1
0.02	(0.008)					478 (69)		1

Fig. 6 Strength Reduction of Uniaxially Loaded Plate With Circular Hole According to Average Stress Criterion (Reference 16)

$$\frac{S_{yy}}{S_0} = \frac{2}{(1+\xi_2)^2 (2+\xi_2^2)}$$

where

$$\xi_2 = \frac{a}{a+a_0}$$

a_0 = characteristic length dimension

S_{yy}, S_0 = strengths of notched and unnotched laminates, respectively.

According to the point stress criterion failure occurs when the axial stress at some distance d_0 from the hole boundary along the transverse axis equals the strength of the unnotched laminate.

Experimental results were compared with predictions by the two criteria above with satisfactory agreement. One experimental result which cannot be described by the criteria above is that there is a limiting hole size below which the laminate becomes notch-insensitive, i.e., failure is as likely to occur through the notched as through the unnotched section. Comparison of the results above with those from similar specimens with cracks showed that strength reduction was nearly independent of notch geometry, i.e., specimens with holes and cracks of the same size had nearly the same strength.

Results for $[0_2/+45]_s$ Laminate

Strains on and near the hole boundary and in the far field were plotted as shown in Fig. 7 for the case of the 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) diameter hole.

In the linear range, the measured stress (strain) concentration factor on the horizontal axis 3.24 is somewhat lower than the theoretical value of 3.44. The compressive strain concentration factor on the vertical axis

Fig. 7 Vertical Strains Along Horizontal Axis of $[0_2/+45]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimen With 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) Diameter Hole Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading

-2.17 is higher than the theoretical value of -1.85. In general, strains on the hole boundary on the horizontal axis become nonlinear at an applied stress of approximately 172 MPa (25 ksi) corresponding to a local strain of 0.0065. Localized failures become audible at this point. Thereafter, the maximum strain on the hole boundary increases nearly linearly at a much reduced rate. The level of first nonlinearity above corresponds to a strain level of over 0.004 on the hole boundary at the 0-degree location. The strain response of the unnotched $[0_2/+45]_S$ laminate in the 90-degree direction becomes appreciably nonlinear at this strain level due to failure of the 0-deg plies. This material nonlinearity at the 0-degree location on the hole boundary produces a stress redistribution around the hole boundary resulting in nonlinear response at the 90-degree location. A second level of pronounced nonlinearity occurs at around 345-415 MPa (50-60 ksi) as a result of stress and strain redistribution produced by localized compressive failure (delamination) on the hole boundary around the vertical axis. Maximum measured strains at failure on the hole boundary are somewhat higher than the ultimate strain of the unnotched laminate.

Isochromatic fringe patterns in the coating reveal points of high birefringence concentration off the horizontal axis at points located between 67- and 72-deg from the loading axis as in the case of the quasi-isotropic laminate. Fringe patterns for a specimen with a 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) diameter hole are shown in Fig. 8. The variation of fringe order and tangential strain at the 0-, 72- and 90-deg locations is shown in Fig. 9. The fringe order at the 0-deg location, proportional to the compressive strain at that point, varies linearly up to an applied stress of 242 MPa (35 ksi) corresponding to a local strain of 0.006. The birefringence at the 90-deg location varies linearly up to a stress of approximately 172 MPa (25 ksi), thereafter it increases at a reduced rate, as was shown by the results from strain gages. The birefringence at the 72-deg location becomes nonlinear at a lower stress of 138 MPa (20 ksi) and it exceeds that at the

Fig. 8 Isochromatic Fringe Patterns in Photoelastic Coating of $[0_2/+45]_s$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimen With 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) Diameter Circular Hole Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading

a) $\sigma_{xx} = 207$ MPa (30 ksi), b) $\sigma_{xx} = 276$ MPa (40 ksi), c) $\sigma_{xx} = 345$ MPa (50 ksi)

Fig. 9 Fringe Order and Circumferential Strain at Three Locations on the Hole Boundary for $[0_2/+45]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimen With 1.91 cm (0.75 in.) Circular Hole Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading

90-deg location.

Failure, for the larger diameter holes, initiated at these characteristic off-axis points. The failure mode changes with decreasing hole diameter. For smaller holes, with diameters smaller than 1.27 cm (0.50 in.), the outer 0-deg plies through the hole tend to delaminate and thus reduce or eliminate the strain concentration at the 90-deg location. Typical failure modes are illustrated in Fig. 10. Additional specimens with smaller diameter holes were tested. Most specimens with holes of 1.57 mm (0.062 in.) diameter and all specimens with 0.41 mm (0.016 in.) or smaller diameter holes failed away from the hole, indicating a critical hole diameter below which the laminate becomes notch-insensitive.

Results for all specimens with holes of diameters between 0.64 cm (0.25 in.) and 2.54 cm (1.00 in.) are tabulated in Table II. Values of the strength reduction ratio for these twelve specimens range between 0.470 and 0.802. The maximum strain measured on the hole boundary at failure ranges between 9.5×10^{-3} and 13.1×10^{-3} compared to an ultimate strain of 10×10^{-3} for the unnotched laminate in the 0-deg direction.

The hole size effect was described using the average stress criterion for the $[0_2/+45]_S$ laminate under uniaxial loading as applied before for the $[0/+45/90]_S$ laminate. For this purpose, an approximate expression suggested by Konish and Whitney (17) was used for the stress distribution along the horizontal axis through the hole:

$$\frac{\sigma_y(x,0)}{\sigma_0} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2} \rho^{-2} + \frac{3}{2} \rho^{-4} - \frac{k_\sigma \rho^{-3}}{2} \quad (5\rho^{-6} - 7\rho^{-8})$$

where

Fig. 10 Failure Patterns in $[0_2/+45]_s$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimens With Holes of Various Sizes Under Uniaxial Tension. (Hole Diameters are 2.54 cm (1 in.), 1.91 cm (0.75 in.), 1.27 cm (0.50 in.) and 0.64 cm (0.25 in.))

Table II. Uniaxially Loaded $[0_2/\pm 45]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Specimens With Circular Holes

Hole Diameter 2a cm (in.)	Modulus E_{xx} GPa (10^6 psi)	Poisson's Ratio, ν_{xy}	Strain Concentration Factor		Strength S_{xxT} MPa (ksi)	Maximum Strain at Failure ($10^{-3}\epsilon$)	Strength Reduction Ratio S_{xxT}/S_o
			$(k_\epsilon)_{90^\circ}$	$(k_\epsilon)_{0^\circ}$			
2.54 (1.00)	84 (12.1)	0.70	3.27		445 (65)	12.3	0.560
2.54 (1.00)	81 (11.8)	0.59	3.43	-2.26	376 (55)	11.3	0.470
2.54 (1.00)	83 (12.0)	0.62	3.02	-2.22	397 (58)	10.0	0.496
1.91 (0.75)	84 (12.2)	0.60	3.37		362 (53)	11.8	0.453
1.91 (0.75)	79 (11.4)	0.67	3.31	-2.03	414 (60)	9.5	0.517
1.91 (0.75)	81 (11.7)	0.62	3.20	-	397 (58)	10.2	0.496
1.27 (0.50)	84 (12.2)	0.68	3.14	-	414 (60)	12.7	0.517
1.27 (0.50)	82 (11.8)	0.66	3.64	-	466 (68)	-	0.582
1.27 (0.50)	82 (11.8)	0.63	3.04	-	486 (71)	12.1	0.608
0.64 (0.25)	84 (12.2)	0.69	3.22	-	414 (60)	12.1	0.517
0.64 (0.25)	81 (11.8)	0.66	3.00	-	600 (87)	13.1	0.750
0.64 (0.25)	81 (11.8)	0.62	-	-	642 (93)	-	0.802

$\sigma_y(x,0)$ = vertical (axial) stress along horizontal axis
 σ_o = applied far-field stress
 ρ = $\frac{x}{a}$
 a = hole radius
 k_o = anisotropic stress concentration factor

According to the average stress criterion applied as before the strength reduction ratio is

$$k_s = \frac{2}{(1+\xi) [2+\xi^2+(k_o-3)\xi^6]}$$

where

$$\xi = \frac{a}{a+a_o}$$

a_o = characteristic length dimension

Experimental results for the strength reduction ratio are in good agreement with theoretical ones based on the average stress criterion for a characteristic length of $a_o = 5$ mm (Fig. 11). The only discrepancies occur for very small and large diameter holes. In the former case, the average stress criterion does not predict the fact that there is a critical hole (notch) size below which the laminate becomes insensitive to it. In the case of large holes local buckling in the compressively stressed part of the hole boundary causes more stress redistribution around the hole near the horizontal axis and alters the failure mode.

Conclusion

The deformation and failure were studied experimentally in uniaxially loaded $[0/+45/90]_s$ quasi-isotropic and $[0_2/+45]_s$ anisotropic graphite/epoxy laminates with circular holes of various diameters. Nonlinearities in the strain variations were associated with first ply failures of the 90-deg plies in the quasi-isotropic laminate and the 0-deg plies in the anisotropic one. Failure initiates at points on the hole boundary located between 67-deg and 72-deg from the loading axis. In the case of the $[0_2/+45]_s$ laminate the failure mode changes for smaller holes, with local delamination of the outer 0-deg plies tending to blunt the stress concentration. The effect of the hole diameter was satisfactorily described using the average stress criterion. In both laminates there is a critical hole diameter below which the laminate becomes notch-insensitive. In the case of the quasi-isotropic laminate it was found that strength reduction is independent of notch geometry.

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Fig. 11 Strength Reduction as a Function of Hole Radius for $[0_2/\pm 45]_S$ Graphite/Epoxy Plates With Circular Holes Under Uniaxial Tensile Loading

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SESSION 13:
NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION (NDE)

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